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DIAGNOSTIC CHARACTERISTIC OF CHILDREN WITH CONGENITAL GLAUCOMA

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Abstract:

In children with suspected glaucoma (megalocornea, myopia, anomaly of the development of optic disc disease), it is compulsory to carry out the following research methods in an in-patient condition: tonography, gonioscopy, ophthalmoscopy. The main diagnostic criteria for the research were gonioscopy-goniodysgenesis of the II and III degree, tonography — true IOP (P0) above 24 mm Hg, Becker coefficient above 100, ophthalmoscopy — sectoral blanching and depth of OD (optic disc) excavation.

Keywords: *suspected glaucoma, congenital glaucoma, goniodysgenesis*

I. Introduction

In the nosological structure of diseases that cause irreversible childhood blindness of the eye congenital pathology is predominant, due to both intrauterine developmental disorders and hereditary factors [4, 5].

Glaucoma is one of the most severe forms of eye pathology, being in a leading place among the causes of blindness and low vision. According to literature, an average of 3% of the world's population (about 70 million people) suffer from glaucoma. However, only half are aware of this diagnosis, and an even smaller percentage of patients receive adequate treatment. At least 7 million patients with glaucoma suffer from blindness in both eyes, and this number is steadily increasing. Such threatening statistics indicate objective difficulties associated with both the diagnosis and treatment of this disease.

Congenital glaucoma (CG) is relatively rare: 1 case per 10-20 thousand newborns [2, 6, 8]. In the countries of the Middle East, there are 1 case of congenital glaucoma in about 2500 births, which is 4 times more than in Western Europe [8, 9]. In some countries, the frequency of this pathology is higher, possibly due to the large number of closely related marriages [1, 3]. It has been noted that an ophthalmologist in the UK identifies a new case of congenital glaucoma every 5 years. According to some authors, among the causes of blindness, the proportion of congenital glaucoma in Europe and North America is 2%, in West Africa and Latin America - 10%, in Asia - 5% [7, 8, 9].

In our country, according to a survey of students from specialized boarding schools for blind and visually impaired children, congenital glaucoma composes 4.2% of the causes of blindness, low vision - 2.2% [5, 6]. Among all eye pathology in children in schools for the blind and visually impaired in Europe, congenital glaucoma constitutes 18% [9]. In the world there are only about 300 thousand patients with congenital glaucoma, of which 75% are blind [3, 7].

Signs of the disease in 60% of children can be detected already in the first 6 months of their life, in 80% - in the first year of life. In 90% of cases of examining newborns in maternity hospitals the disease can be diagnosed with early signs [5].

Primary congenital glaucoma (PCG or hydrophthalmus) is manifested in children at the age of under 3 years old, recessive inheritance (sporadic cases are possible), with pathological mechanism of anterior chamber angle dysgenesis (ACA) and increased IOP, and clinical symptoms including photophobia, lacrimation, blepharospasm, enlarged eyeball, swelling and an increase in the size of the cornea, excavation of optic discs.

The relentless interest of ophthalmologists in congenital glaucoma is largely due to the variety of clinical manifestations, the complexity of the pathogenesis and the severity of the consequences of this disease.

Thus, despite studies aimed at studying the etiology, pathogenesis, diagnosis and treatment of congenital glaucoma, the problem of this disease remains relevant and requires further research.

Purpose of the study. Identifying the main differential diagnostic criteria for examining children with suspected glaucoma.

Material and research methods: from 2016 to 2019, we examined 50 children (91 eyes) aged 20 days to 14 years in the eye department of the TashPMI clinic. The group did not include children with secondary, combined glaucoma and children with systemic diseases.

All children were hospitalized on an emergency basis, after preparation, all patients underwent anti-glaucomatous surgery. Of the examined patient boys made up 28 (56%), girls 22 (44%).

All patients were divided into 2 groups:

Group I (main) included 33 (66%) patients (64 eyes) with suspected congenital glaucoma;

Group II (control) included 17 (34%) children (27 eyes) with congenital glaucoma.

All patients underwent the following research methods: ophthalmological (visometry, external examination, tonometry, Friedenwaldtonography, biomicroscopy, gonioscopy, target pressure, ophthalmoscopy (direct and indirect), ultrasound (A, B scanning), clinical and laboratory methods, specialist consultations (pediatrician, neurologist, otolaryngologist, anesthetist).

II. Results of the study: Following eye pathology was revealed in children of the 1st group, ametropia - myopia in 33 (50%); diseases of the anterior segment of the eyeball in 23 (35%); diseases of the posterior segment of the eyeball in 10 (15%).

Children of the 2nd group were distributed depending on the type of glaucoma: with congenital primary glaucoma - 17 (94%), of which 2 (12%) with hydrophthalmus, 9 (53%) with infantile, 1 (6%) patient with glaucoma associated with systemic congenital syndromes. The distribution of patients according to the stages of the process showed that the largest percentage was late (55%) and terminal (11%) stages of congenital glaucoma.

During biomicroscopy in children of group II, the cornea increased in diameter (12-14 mm) was observed in all 27 (100%) eyes. The average diameter of the cornea was 12.6 ± 0.3 mm. Gaaba lines, stromal edema, corneal opacity, limb enlargement of more than 2 mm., Iris atrophy was observed in all 27 (100%) patients. In patients of group I, these indicators were distributed as follows: Gaaba lines were observed in 19 (30%), stromal edema in 20 (31%), corneal clouding in 23 (36%), limb enlargement of more than 2 mm in 24 (42%), atrophy of the iris in 13 (20%) cases, respectively.

A comparative analysis of the ophthalmological parameters of the optic nerve head (optic disc) in children of groups I and II showed that in patients with stage II, the ratio of excavation to disk area (E / D) is 0.5-0.8 and above 0.8, the depth of excavation: deep and sectoral blanching of the neuroretinal girdle (NRG) in the outer and lower segments was observed in all 27 (100%) cases, respectively (Table 1).

Table 1.
Comparative analysis of ophthalmoscopic data in children of groups I and II

Ophthalmic Pathology	Group I				Group II	
	Pathology of the anterior segment	Pathology of the posterior segment		Ametropia		
Symptoms	Megalocornea n=16	Fovea of Optic disc n=2	Oblique entry of the optic disc n= 8	Mediumdegree Myopia n=18	High degree Myopia n=15	
Size of excavation						

with regard to optic disc						
Less than 0,3	6 (37%)			12 (36%)	9 (27%)	6 (22%)
0,3-0,5	6 (37%)	2 (20%)	8 (80%)	1 (3%)	2 (6%)	13 (48%)
0,5-0,8	2 (12%)			3 (9%)	3 (9%)	8 (30%)
Above 0,8	2 (12%)			2 (6%)	1 (3%)	
Depth of excavation						
Superficial	2 (12%)	2 (20%)	8 (80%)	1 (3%)		
Medium	4 (25%)			11 (33%)	9 (27%)	
Deep	10 (62%)			6 (18%)	6 (18%)	27(100%)
Sectoral blanching of neuroretina						
I girdle	6 (37%)					
Absent	3 (19%)	2 (20%)	8 (80%)	12 (36%)	9 (27%)	9(33%)
Interior	5 (31%)			3 (9%)	3 (9%)	18 (67%)
Outer	2 (12%)			3 (9%)	4 (12%)	
Lower						

In patients of group I: E / D above normal (from 0.3 to 0.8 and more than 0.8) was observed in 22 (34%); excavation depth: deep in 22 (34%), sectoral blanching of the neuroretinal girdle in the outer and lower segments in 20 (31%) cases, respectively.

Analysis of the results of gonioscopy in most patients of group I (72%), the anterior chamber angle was opened. Goniodysgenesis of the I degree was observed in 7 (39%), II degree in 4 (22%), and III degrees in 7 (39%) eyes, respectively. In children of group II, goniodysgenesis of degree II prevailed with 44%.

According to tonometry and tonography, in most children of the second group of IOP, the tonometric P10 (27.8 ± 0.3 mmHg) and true IOP (P0) (24.98 ± 1.1 mmHg) were increased. Becker coefficient made up 301.3 ± 3.0 . In children of group I P10, within the normal range (19.6 ± 0.03) in 37 (58%), and above the norm (from 24.91 to 27.5 ± 0.03 mm Hg) in 32 (42%) eyes, respectively. An increase in P0 was observed (26.17 ± 0.03 mm Hg) in 15 (23%), normal limits (19.63 ± 0.03 mm Hg) – in 49 (77%) eyes, respectively. The Becker coefficient was increased in 4 (6%) eyes and composed 141.33 ± 2.5 , and in the other remaining eyes averaged 65.5 ± 1.3 .

Thus, out of 33 children with suspected glaucoma, a diagnosis was confirmed in 9 (27%) children (18 eyes) based on tonography, gonioscopy and ophthalmoscopy.

Based on the classification of congenital glaucoma according to N.A. Kachan, T.K. Toikuliev (2004), patients were diagnosed with the initial stage of congenital primary glaucoma in 4 (8.9%) eyes, the developed stage in 7 (15.6%) eyes and long-term glaucoma in 30 (66.7%) eyes. The terminal stage of glaucoma was observed in 4 (8.9%) eyes.

Congenital glaucoma is an indication for emergency surgical treatment, since high pressure leads to compression of the optic nerve, which in turn leads to a decrease in visual acuity.

III. Conclusions:

1. The diagnosis of suspected glaucoma was mainly detected in children with anomalies in the development of optic disc (15%), with megalocornea (37%) and with myopia (50%). Of these, the

diagnosis of glaucoma was confirmed in 9 (27%) children. In 24 (73%) children the diagnosis is not confirmed.

2. The main diagnostic criteria of research were gonioscopy-goniodysgenesis grade II and III, tonography — true IOP (P0) above 24 mm Hg, Becker coefficient above 100, ophthalmoscopy — sectoral blanching and depth of OD excavation.

3. In most cases, among children with congenital glaucoma there is a late stage - 66.7%, in rare cases, the initial - 8.9% and terminal stages - 8.9%.

References

1. Bratko O.V. Clinical evaluation of biomechanical features of the fibrous membrane of the eye in patients with glaucoma in combination with myopic refraction // Abstract. dis. .k. honey. sciences. Samara 2010. -FROM. 21-26.
2. Gusarevich O. G., Fursova A. Zh., Fenkova O. G. The central thickness of the cornea with congenital glaucoma, suspected glaucoma // Collection of scientific papers of a scientific and practical conference with international participation, dedicated to the 110th anniversary of the Moscow Scientific Research Institute of GB named after Helmholtz. - Moscow, 2010. - Volume 2. - P. 267-273.
3. Katargina L.A. et al. Importance of modern imaging methods for anomalies of the anterior segment of the eye and congenital glaucoma in children // Russian Ophthalmological Journal-2012.-№2.-P.7-11.
4. Katargina L.A., Tarasenkov A.O., Mazanova E.V. On the classification of congenital glaucoma by stages // Russian Pediatric Ophthalmology.-2016.-11-No. 4.-S. P. 179-182.
5. Khamroeva Yu.A., Khamraeva L.S. The role of biomechanical parameters of the eye in the development of congenital glaucoma in children. Russian Pediatric Ophthalmology, 2014, No. 2, P.30-31.
6. Khamroeva Yu.A. Buzrukov B.T. Comparative analysis of the size of the anteroposterior axes of the eyes with congenital glaucoma and healthy eyes in the age aspect. Clinical Ophthalmology. 2013, No. 1, P.17.
7. Berg C, Doniger SJ, Zaia B, Williams SR. Change in intraocular pressure during point-of-care ultrasound. West J Emerg Med. 2015 Mar; 16 (2): 263-8.
8. Davis R, Jiramongkolchai K, Silverstein E, Freedman SF. Rebound tonometry over an air-filled anterior chamber in the supine child after intraocular surgery. J AAPOS. 2016 Apr; 20 (2): 159-64.
9. Yang B., Ye C., Yu M. et al. Optic disc imaging with spectral-domain optical coherence tomography: variability and agreement study with Heidelberg retinal tomograph // Ophthalmology. - 2012. - Vol. 119, No. 9. - P. 1852-1857